

1 **Effect of breed and lithium chloride dose on the conditioned**
2 **aversion to olive tree leaves (*Olea europaea* L.) of sheep**

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15

16 *Key words:*

17 Food aversion

18 Olive tree

19 Sheep

20 Breed

21

22

23 **ABSTRACT**

24 Grazing maybe an efficient tool for controlling weed cover in olive groves.

25 However, olive leaves are very palatable for sheep, which damages the trees

26 and compromised the later olive production. Lithium chloride (LiCl) is an
27 effective agent for creating food aversion in ruminants through the activation of
28 the emetic system. We investigated the response in three sheep breeds
29 (Manchega, Lacaune and Ripollesa; $N = 15$ for each breed) to two doses of LiCl
30 (AV1, 200; AV2, 225 mg/kg BW) for averting adult ewes to olive tree leaves
31 compared to a control group (C, water blank). The aversion was reinforced on
32 day nine in those ewes that consumed >10 g of olive leaves. Persistence was
33 evaluated by a double-choice feeding assay, where 100 g of olive leaves were
34 offered side-by-side with 400 g of rye-grass (as fed), at several intervals across
35 70 days. Intake and persistence were compared between doses and breeds.
36 Significant breed effects in the controls suggested a genetic component in
37 neophobia (i.e., Ripollesa and Manchega were neophobic whereas Lacaune
38 was not). Aversion was fully created with a single dose in all ewes, however,
39 20% of animals needed a reinforcement dose to strengthen the aversion
40 (especially in Manchega ewes and AV1 dose). Total aversion persisted 54 days
41 in AV2 and 33 days in AV1, whereas that differences only presented a tendency
42 in Manchega breed ($P = 0.058$). Effective aversion length of AV1 vs. C varied by
43 breed (Manchega $<$ Lacaune = Ripollesa), but those differences were not
44 detected in AV2 for which all the breeds showed less olive leaf intake until the
45 end of the experiment (day 70, $P < 0.001$). In conclusion, breed affected
46 aversion persistence at a 200 mg LiCl/kg BW dose. However, a dose of 225 mg
47 LiCl/kg BW with a reinforced dose might mitigate the breed effect.

48

49 **1. Introduction**

50

51 The olive tree (*Olea europaea* L.) is an important crop in Spain which, with
52 nearly 2.5×10^6 ha and more than 1 Mt/year of olive oil production, is the
53 largest olive oil producer and exporter in the world (MAGRAMA, 2013). Olive
54 grove pruning residues (branches with green leaves) are usually fed to
55 ruminants in most producing countries because they are very palatable and
56 nutritive (Nefzaoui, 1988). As a consequence of their high acceptability,
57 landowners do not use to graze sheep and goat in olive groves in order to
58 prevent damage to the trees and crop losses.

59 The use of a controlled green cover (i.e., natural or cultivated grass) under
60 the olive trees is considered as a recommended cultural practice to prevent soil
61 erosion, thus increasing water, organic carbon and nitrate retention (Alonso and
62 Guzmán, 2006). Controlled grazing by small ruminants may be used as an
63 alternative to reduce weeds land cover during spring, for conserving soil
64 moisture, and to improve soil fertility, while avoiding the use of labour,
65 machinery and herbicides.

66 Aversive conditioning is a form of associative learning behaviour in which an
67 animal avoids consuming a food previously paired with a malaise–illness effect
68 (unconditioned stimulus). It is considered a useful method for training livestock
69 to avoid specific food or plants. The efficiency of conditioned aversion depends
70 on food novelty (Burritt and Provenza, 1989), product used to create the
71 aversion (Zahorik et al., 1990; Conover, 1995), product dose (Egber et al.,
72 1998), availability of an alternative feed (Thorhallsdottir et al., 1990b; Gorniak et
73 al., 2008), animal species (Manuelian et al., 2010) and age (Thorhallsdottir et
74 al., 1987, 1990a).

75 Conditioned aversion using lithium chloride (LiCl) has been used as a
76 potential management tool to avoid palatable foods and/or poisonous plants in
77 domestic livestock (Ralphs and Provenza, 1999; Ralphs et al., 2001; Manuelian
78 et al., 2010). The LiCl is a water-soluble, easy-to-dose and safe (Prien et al.,
79 1971) product for animal use. After administration, LiCl produces digestive
80 malaise due to the activation of the emetic system (Provenza et al., 1994)
81 followed by a quick recovery thereafter (Burritt and Provenza, 1989; Provenza
82 ,1995). Recommended LiCl dose for sheep in practice is 200 mg/kg BW (du Toit
83 et al., 1991; Egber et al., 1998). Despite the significant variability reported in the
84 voluntary intake of food in the averted animals, there is no evidence of a breed
85 effect.

86 The objective of this experiment was to evaluate the response of three sheep
87 breeds to two LiCl doses for inducing conditioned aversion to olive tree leaves.

88

89 **2. Material and methods**

90

91 The experiment was carried out at the Experimental Farm of the SGCE
92 (Servei de Granges i Camps Experimentals) of the Universitat Autònoma de
93 Barcelona (Bellaterra, Spain) during late winter and spring. The experimental
94 procedures and animal care conditions were approved by the Ethical
95 Committee of Animal and Human Experimentation (CEEAH, reference 770) of
96 the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona.

97

98 *2.1. Animals and management*

99

100 A total of 15 Manchega dairy ewes (43.5 ± 0.9 kg BW), 15 Lacaune dairy
101 ewes (54.7 ± 1.3 kg BW), and 15 Ripollesa meat ewes (45.0 ± 1.2 kg BW) were
102 used in 3 parallel experiments for assessing the use of LiCl in conditioned
103 aversion to olive leaves. Ewes were adult, dry and non-pregnant; and naïve to
104 olive leaves. They grazed during the day (6 h/day) in an Italian rye-grass
105 (*Lolium multiflorum* Lam.) pasture and received tall fescue hay (*Festuca*
106 *arundinacea* L.) ad libitum in the shelter. Water and a commercial block of
107 vitamins and minerals (Multi-Block, Agraria Comarcal del Vallès, Les
108 Franqueses, Barcelona, Spain) were permanently available in the shelter.

109 Leaves of olive tree (cv. Arbequina) were obtained at the end of the harvest
110 season (January) from an olive cooperative (La Palma d'Ebre, Tarragona,
111 Spain). The cv. Arbequina represents the most used olive tree cultivar in
112 Catalonia (NE of Spain). The leaves were air-dried for 1 week and stored at
113 room temperature until fed. With the aim of offering the olive leaves in a double
114 choice feeding assay, Italian rye-grass was manually harvested every day from
115 the grazing fields at vegetative phenological stage and stored at room
116 temperature until used.

117 Samples of olive leaves, rye-grass and tall fescue hay used during the
118 experiment were taken weekly, composited by treatment group, and stored
119 under refrigeration (4°C) until analysis.

120 Figure 1 represents schematically the experimental design and the days
121 were measurements were taken throughout the study.

122

123 *2.2. Creation of conditioning aversion (learning period)*

124

125 At the start of the experiment, ewes were individually penned in box stalls
126 (1.1 × 2.0 m) and randomly allocated into 3 groups of 5 animals for each breed,
127 to which experimental treatments were applied. Visual contact between animals
128 of different groups was avoided. Ewes received a basal diet of tall fescue hay
129 ad libitum once a day and were adapted to the experimental facilities for 1-week
130 prior to starting with the conditioned aversion creation.

131 Treatments consisted of 2 aversion conditioned groups of different LiCl doses
132 (AV1, 200; AV2, 225 mg/kg BW) and a control group (C). Lithium chloride
133 (Panreac, Castellar del Vallés, Barcelona, Spain) was orally administered in a
134 water solution using a 200 mL drenching gun (Pimex, Abadiño, Vizcaya, Spain)
135 as indicated by Manuelian et al. (2010). On the day of aversion creation (day 0),
136 fescue hay was removed 2 h before each ewe received 100 g olive leaves, as
137 fed, for 1 h. Then, AV1 and AV2 ewes were conditioned by pairing the olive
138 leaves (novel food) with the LiCl (unconditioned stimulus), whereas C ewes
139 received 100 mL of water to equalize the drenching effect (blank). Olive leaf
140 intake was measured by weight difference, and animal eating behaviour and
141 olive leaf spillage, if occurring, was recorded. On the next 2 days (day one and
142 two) 100 g of olive leaves were offered for 1-h to each ewe to validate aversion.
143 Validation was also done on days nine and 10, after the double-choice test in
144 the box stalls. Dosage of LiCl was repeated for any AV1 or AV2 ewe that
145 consumed more than 10 g as fed of olive leaves at day nine, to reinforce their
146 aversion.

147 Basal diet intake was recorded daily as a means of evaluating discomfort in
148 the animals. Usual intake level was calculated according to the pre-treatment
149 average consumption of olive leaves.

150

151 *2.3. Double-choice feeding test in individual box-stall pens*

152

153 On day three, a double-choice feeding test was carried out during six
154 consecutive days to evaluate aversion food persistence. Aversion persistence
155 was defined according to Massei and Cowan (2002) as the number of post-
156 conditioning encounters after which the animal re-samples the averted feed (in
157 our case, 10 g or more of olive leaves). Moreover, aversion was considered
158 effective (LiCl effect remaining) when the averted ewes ate less olive leaves
159 than the C ewes.

160 The double-choice feeding test consisted of recording the intake of two
161 separated feeds offered at the same time with the same amount of dry matter.
162 Olive leaves (averted feed, 100 g as fed) and Italian rye-grass (alternative feed,
163 390 g as fed) were offered for 1 h in individual plastic containers (38 × 26.5 ×
164 15.5 cm; Araven, Zaragoza, Spain) placed side-by-side. Container positions
165 were switched daily to prevent possible eating habits, since one position might
166 be perceived as more convenient by the animal (Meier et al., 2012). Differences
167 in animal behaviour throughout feeding tests and days elapsed until olive leaves
168 were again eaten after aversion creation was also recorded. No additional LiCl
169 doses were given.

170 After validating the conditioned aversion on day nine and 10, all the ewes
171 joined the Experimental farm's flock for grazing and were also supplemented
172 indoors as previously indicated.

173

174 *2.4. Double-choice feeding assay in the shelter*

175

176 To extend the persistence study, double-choice feeding assays were also
177 done in the barn using the head-lockers of the feed bunk for individual
178 restraining. Each double-choice test lasted 30 min and cross consumption of
179 feeds was prevented by leaving empty two places between ewes. Test-days
180 recorded were: 21, 28, 34, 42, 55, and 70 days after the first LiCl dose on day
181 zero and the same protocol as explained in 2.3. was followed.

182

183 *2.5. Feed composition analyses*

184

185 Dry matter was determined at 103°C for 24 h and ash content was measured
186 gravimetrically by igniting samples in a muffle furnace at 550°C for 4 h (AOAC,
187 2000). The Dumas method (AOAC, 2000) with a Leco analyzer (Leco
188 Corporation, St. Joseph, MI) was used for N determination and crude protein
189 was calculated as percentage of N × 6.25. Neutral detergent fibre, acid
190 detergent fibre and lignin were determined on an ash-free basis by the method
191 of Van Soest (1982) using the Ankom200 Fiber Analyzer incubator (Ankom
192 Technology, Macedon, NY), adding amylase and sodium sulphite solutions.
193 Olive leaf, tall fescue hay and Italian rye-grass chemical compositions are
194 shown in Table 1.

195

196 *2.6. Statistical analyses*

197

198 Data of olive leaf intake showed a non normal distribution that was not
199 normalised using Box-Cox transformations (Box-Cox , Cox, 1964; Osborne,

200 2010). As a consequence, treatment and breed effects were analysed using a
201 non parametric Kruskal-Wallis test of SPSS v. 19.0.0 of IBM (Chicago, IL,
202 USA). Aversion persistency data were studied by survival analysis using the
203 Kaplan-Meier non-parametric and log-rank (Mantel-Cox) tests of equality of
204 SPSS across treatments and breeds. Tall fescue hay basal diet intake was
205 analysed by metabolic body weight using a linear mixed model with repeated
206 measure, and differences tested by LS Means of R 3.0.2 (R Core Team, 2013).
207 Values are shown as mean \pm SE or as median (for survival analyses), and
208 significance was declared at $P < 0.05$ unless otherwise indicated.

209

210 **3. Results**

211

212 *3.1. Neophobic behaviour*

213

214 Intake of olive leaves showed marked differences between ewe breeds
215 before applying the aversion treatments at day zero ($H_2 = 27.9$; $P = 0.001$), and
216 values were greater ($H_1 = 8.87$; $P = 0.003$) in Lacaune (87 ± 6 g) than in
217 Manchega (60 ± 8 g), and being greater ($H_1 = 12.30$; $P = 0.001$) in Manchega
218 than in Ripollesa (20 ± 3 g). Lacaune C ewes consumed almost all the olive
219 leaves offered from the first day and their intake was similar thereafter (Fig. 2a).
220 Manchega C ewes gradually increased the intake of olive leaves during the first
221 week and their intake steadied thereafter (Fig. 2b). On the other hand, Ripollesa
222 C ewes showed the lowest initial intake of olive leaves, which dramatically
223 incremented during the first week. Moreover, Ripollesa C ewes showed the
224 largest intake variability across the testing days with a similar plateau (Fig. 2c)

225 and final intake value equalling the other breeds (86 ± 4 g, on average; $H_2 =$
226 0.27 ; $P = 0.873$). Neophobia degree, expressed as the percentage of olive leaf
227 refusal on the first day before applying the aversion treatments (day zero) with
228 regard to the mean final intake value (day 70), were 1.1, 30.2 and 76.7% for
229 Lacaune, Manchega and Ripollesa breeds, respectively.

230

231 *3.2. Conditioning aversion learning*

232

233 With the exception of one AV1 Manchega ewe, which spat out most of the
234 dose on day zero and received a second dose on day two, AV1 and AV2 groups
235 fully rejected consuming olive leaves on day one ($H_2 = 42.03$; $P = 0.001$) and
236 day two ($H_2 = 40.93$; $P = 0.001$) after LiCl dosing (Fig. 2).

237 Differences in ewe behaviour pattern between groups were observed after
238 LiCl administration (day one and two) in the box-stall pens. Averted ewes did
239 not approach or sniff the containers with olive leaves and fully rejected
240 consuming them. The basal diet intake decreased 34.9 % in the treated ewes
241 after LiCl administration on day zero (AV1, 48.0 ± 6.1 g/kg $BW^{0.75}$; AV2, $45.2 \pm$
242 6.0 g/kg $BW^{0.75}$; $P < 0.033$). AV 1 ewes needed 1 day to recover the intake level,
243 whereas AV2 ewes needed 2 days. On day 1 there were also differences in
244 fescue hay intake between doses (AV1, 57.4 ± 4.1 g/kg $BW^{0.75}$; AV2, 44.2 ± 5.6
245 g/kg $BW^{0.75}$; $P < 0.033$). Additionally, the averted ewes showed drooped head
246 and ears, and inactivity. Regarding breeds, both AV2 Manchega and Ripollesa
247 ewes recovered usual intake level one day later than AV1 ewes. However, AV1
248 and AV2 Lacaune ewes did not show that difference.

249 On day three and following days, intake of olive leaves in the box-stall pens
250 varied according to breed and LiCl dose (Fig. 2). On average, AV2 ewes of all
251 breeds rejected consuming olive leaves until day nine, although one Manchega
252 ewe (20%) showed slight olive leaf intake (2 to 12 g/day) at days four, six and
253 nine and was reinforced. With regard to AV1, the Ripollesa ewes maintained a
254 total aversion to olive leaves during the 9-day period but, three Manchega
255 (60%) and two Lacaune (40%) ewes increased progressively the intake of olive
256 leaves (>10 g/d), from 3 to 9 and 5 to 9 days, respectively. These ewes were
257 reinforced with a second LiCl dose at day nine and their full aversion was re-
258 established on day 10. Nevertheless, aversion effects were still evident on day
259 nine, where the AV1 ewes showed lower intake than C ewes in each breed
260 (Manchega, $H_1 = 5.54$; $P = 0.019$; Lacaune, $H_1 = 7.18$; $P = 0.005$; Ripollesa, H_1
261 $= 7.81$; $P = 0.005$).

262 Differences in intake reduction of olive leaves in favour of AV2, when
263 compared to AV1 doses, were only detected on day three ($H_1 = 6.10$; $P = 0.013$)
264 and seven ($H_1 = 5.67$; $P = 0.017$) in the Manchega ewes. Moreover, a tendency
265 was also observed for days four, five, six, eight and nine ($P = 0.052$ to 0.072) in
266 that breed, and in the Lacaune ewes for days six, eight and nine ($P = 0.054$ to
267 0.136). No differences between AV1 and AV2 doses were detected in the
268 Ripollesa ewes averted groups ($H_1 = 0.00$; $P = 1.000$).

269

270 3.3. Persistence of the aversion: double-choice feeding assay

271

272 Appetence of rye-grass during the double-choice test, assessed by
273 comparing the proportion of rye-grass eaten (ingested/offered $\times 100$) averaged

274 92.2 ± 0.9% and did not differ by treatment ($H_2 = 2.95$; $P = 0.229$) or breed ($H_2 =$
275 2.06; $P = 0.358$) throughout the study. Persistence of aversion, evaluated using
276 survival analysis as the days during which ewes refused consumption of the
277 olive leaves after the first LiCl dose (aversion learning), tended to show a dose
278 effect. On average, the aversion of AV2 ewes persisted longer (median survival
279 time, 54 days; range, 28 to 80 days) than that of AV1 ewes (median survival
280 time, 33 days; range, 16 to 51 days; $X_1^2 = 3.35$; $P = 0.067$). Nevertheless, when
281 data were analyzed by breed, difference between AV1 and AV2 was only
282 detected as a tendency in the Manchega ewes ($X_1^2 = 3.58$; $P = 0.058$; Fig. 3).

283 With regard to effective aversion length, olive leaf intake of the averted
284 ewes vs. C ewes, varied by LiCl dose, being 55 days for AV1 (intake at day 55,
285 38 ± 8 g vs. 84 ± 6 g; $H_1 = 11.0$; $P = 0.001$) and 70 for AV2 (intake at day 70, 49
286 ± 7 vs. 86 ± 4 g; $H_1 = 16.1$; $P < 0.001$), respectively. Moreover, effective
287 aversion length of AV1 treated ewes vs. C ewes varied by breed: Manchega
288 (intake day 34, 65 ± 23 g vs. 100 ± 0 g; $H_1 = 3.72$; $P = 0.054$; Fig. 3b), Lacaune
289 (intake day 55, 21 ± 9 g vs. 87 ± 18 g; $H_1 = 3.75$; $P = 0.053$; Fig. 3a) and
290 Ripollesa (intake day 55, 47 ± 18 g vs. 85 ± 10 g; $H_1 = 3.23$; $P = 0.072$; Fig. 3c).
291 No differences by breed were observed in effective aversion length for the AV2
292 dose vs. C: Manchega (intake day 70, 63 ± 7 g vs. 90 ± 5 g; $H_1 = 5.0$; $P = 0.025$;
293 Fig. 3b), Lacaune (intake day 70, 43 ± 13 g vs. 87 ± 3 g; $H_1 = 7.25$; $P = 0.007$;
294 Fig. 3a) and Ripollesa (intake day 70, 41 ± 15 g vs. 83 ± 11 g; $H_1 = 3.84$; $P =$
295 0.050; Fig. 3c), respectively.

296

297 *3.4. Re-establishing conditioned aversion*

298

299 Aversion behaviour of the reinforced ewes varied markedly according to
300 breed and LiCl dose indicating a genetic component in the response to
301 conditioned aversion. The Manchega ewes needing a second LiCl dose (three
302 AV1 and one AV2) were also the earliest to resume olive leaf consumption at
303 days 21 and 28, respectively. On the other hand, two AV1 Lacaune ewes
304 needed reinforcement, whereas one of them resumed at day 55. No Ripollesa
305 ewes needed to be reinforced.

306

307 **4. DISCUSSION**

308

309 *4.1. Neophobic behaviour*

310

311 The avoidance of a new or unfamiliar feed is described as an innate
312 protective mechanism (neophobic behaviour), which allows animals to learn
313 from the post-ingestive consequences of eating a potentially toxic feed (Van
314 Tien et al., 1999). With regard to the olive leaves used in our study, despite all
315 the ewes being naïve, only Manchega and Ripollesa breed expressed
316 neophobia on the first days. Intake of olive leaves gradually increased and
317 steadied thereafter indicating the final acceptance of the new feed (Fig.1).
318 Neophobic behaviour was previously reported in crossbred lambs and ewes
319 offered unfamiliar feeds by Thorhallsdottir et al. (1987; rolled barley and rabbit
320 pellets) and Pfister et al. (1993; corn). Moreover, Villalba et al. (2012) described
321 a similar behaviour using unfamiliar flavours (coconut, cinnamon and onion) in
322 crossbred lambs.

323 Villalba et al. (2009) observed the relationship between reluctance to eat
324 novel foods and lamb's temperament in different breeds (white-faced
325 Rambouillet-Columbia-Finn-Targhee or black-faced Suffolk crossbreeds), and
326 suggested that there is a genetic component in feeding neophobic behaviour.
327 Interestingly, our Ripollesa ewes (local meat breed) were strongly neophobic,
328 Manchega (medium yield dairy breed) were intermediate and Lacaune ewes
329 (high yield dairy breed) did not express any neophobic behaviour, which may be
330 a consequence of the degree of genetic selection applied in each breed. Olive
331 leaf intake of the C ewe groups was high and similar in the 3 breeds at the end
332 of the study, indicating that they were palatable for sheep.

333

334 *4.2. Conditioning aversion learning*

335

336 Aversion to olive leaves was fully established in the short term with a single
337 dose of LiCl in most AV1 and in all AV2 ewes. A similar response to LiCl was
338 reported by Manuelian et al. (2010) in sheep and goats averted to olive leaves
339 using a 200 mg LiCl/kg BW dose. The only Manchega ewe that was redosed
340 (day two) was as a consequence of the incomplete swallowing of the AV1 dose
341 administered. Lower aversion rates (65 to 75%) to the first LiCl dose (130 to
342 200 mg LiCl/kg BW) were reported in small ruminants and the non-averted
343 animals needed a new dose of LiCl on the following day to achieve the full
344 aversion (Pfister et al., 1993; Burrit and Provenza, 1996; Gorniak et al., 2008).

345 Nefzaoui (1989) reported differences in composition and digestibility
346 between green and dry olive tree pruning residues. On average, dry matter
347 digestibility is greater in the green (56.9%) than in the dry leaves (48.2%).

348 These moderate differences seem not to be enough to show differences in
349 aversion behaviour. With this regard, other studies (C.L. Manuelian,
350 unpublished data) showed that goats averted to dry olive leaves also refused to
351 eat green olive leaves under on-field conditions.

352

353 *4.3. Dose effect*

354

355 Head droop, inactivity and decrease basal diet intake the days following
356 LiCl administration are described by Pfister et al. (1993) as signs of discomfort.
357 This behaviour pattern was more evident in the AV2 than in AV1 ewes, as
358 supported by basal diet intake data. AV2 ewes needed more days to recover the
359 daily intake after dosing, which suggested that their discomfort after the LiCl
360 dose was higher than for the AV1 group. Moreover, a higher ratio of AV1 ewes
361 needed to be reinforced to strengthen the aversion. These results complete and
362 support the dose-dependent relationship found between feed intake and LiCl
363 dose (du Toit et al., 1991; Egber et al., 1998), the aversion being greater with
364 the higher LiCl dose (i.e., AV2 > AV1).

365

366 *4.4. Breed effect*

367

368 Breed was not previously reported as a factor modifying the persistence of
369 conditioned aversion (Conover, 1995; Ralph et al., 2001) but, our results
370 supported the idea that breed has to be considered as a variation factor in
371 aversion persistence studies. In practice, the short persistent breeds need to be
372 reinforced with a second dose, as observed with the Manchega and Lacaune

373 ewes in our study. On the contrary, Ripollesa ewes did not need reinforcement.
374 Nevertheless, the extent of breed effect was also related to the LiCl dose.
375 Differences in effectiveness of aversion between breeds were only detected
376 with the AV1 dose, the AV2 ewes being more persistent regardless of the breed.
377 Our results also suggested that breed differences in conditioned aversion food
378 can be abolished when a high dose of LiCl is used.

379

380 **4. Conclusions**

381

382 The results of this study highlight the differences in neophobic food
383 behaviour to olive leaves according to breed and further support the concept
384 that food aversion persistence is dose dependent. Moreover, we proved for the
385 first time that the acquisition of associative learning behaviour was different
386 according to breed.

387 Finally, differences between breeds were greater at the low LiCl dose,
388 indicating that sensitivity to LiCl depends on breed and dose. Consequently,
389 persistence of the conditioned aversion to olive leaves in sheep was longer with
390 the 225 mg LiCl/kg BW dose; additionally, fewer ewes needed to be re-
391 enforced.

392

393 **Acknowledgements**

394

395 This work is part of a CICYT research project (AGL 2010-22178) of the
396 Spanish Ministry of Science and Technology. The authors are grateful to Dr.
397 Jordi Bartolomé (Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Bellaterra, Spain) for

398 supplying the olive tree leaves; to Ramon Costa and the team of the Servei de
399 Granges i Camps Experimentals of the UAB (Bellaterra, Spain) for technical
400 assistance and care of the animals; and to Nic Aldam (Barcelona, Spain) for the
401 English revision of the manuscript.

402

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490 **Table 1.** Chemical composition of tall fescue hay, dry olive leaves and Italian rye
491 grass pasture (DM basis). Values are means \pm ES.

492 **Fig. 1.** Synopsis of experimental design and measurements taken during the
493 study. (A, adaptation period; CA, creation of conditioning aversion, DC, double-
494 choice feeding test; VA, validation aversion; R, non experimental period; Δ ,
495 measurement day in the adaptation period; \triangle , measurement day with lithium
496 chloride (LiCl) administration; \blacktriangle , measurement day without LiCl administration).

497 **Fig. 2.** Intake of olive leaves during the aversion conditioned experiment
498 according to treatment (\circ , control; \blacktriangle , AV1, 200 mg LiCl/kg BW; \blacksquare , AV2, 225 mg
499 LiCl/kg BW) and sheep breed: (a) Lacaune, (b) Manchega, (c) Ripollesa.

500 Application of LiCl treatment ($\hat{\uparrow}$, AV1, 200 mg LiCl/kg BW; $\hat{\uparrow}$, AV2, 225 mg
501 LiCl/kg BW). Values are means \pm SE.

502 **Fig. 3.** Frequency of averted ewes by groups (---, AV1, 200 mg LiCl/kg BW; ...,
503 AV2, 225 mg LiCl/kg BW) and by sheep breed: (a) Lacaune, (b) Manchega, (c)
504 Ripollesa.

505

Nutrient content, %	Fescue hay	Olive leaves	Rye grass
Dry matter	89.57 ± 0.20	78.25 ± 0.03	20.02 ± 0.01
Crude protein	15.02 ± 0.21	9.33 ± 0.00	20.24 ± 1.32
Crude fibre	25.55 ± 0.04	16.49 ± 0.15	19.15 ± 0.74
Neutral detergent fibre	54.95 ± 0.15	40.61 ± 0.49	40.40 ± 0.52
Acid detergent fibre	28.60 ± 0.23	27.74 ± 0.63	21.64 ± 0.16
Lignin acid detergent	2.12 ± 0.20	15.71 ± 0.48	4.87 ± 0.04
Ash	9.87 ± 0.08	9.13 ± 0.04	13.37 ± 0.01

Figure

a) Lacaune

b) Manchega

c) Ripollesa

a) Lacaune

b) Manchega

c) Ripollesa

